

Comparative Study of 'Zone' Diffusion and 'Front' Diffusion

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Both 'front' diffusion and 'zone' diffusion of $^{131}\text{I}^-$ in 0.01 M KNO_3 in 2.5% agar gel obey Fick's second law. However, the rate of diffusion in 'front' diffusion is dependent on the time as well as the distance from the plane of contact whereas it is independent of the time in 'zone' diffusion.

A knowledge of diffusion coefficient of electrolytes in aqueous solutions is of fundamental interest in unravelling the intricate problems of meagerly understood ion-solvent interactions. Radiotracer technique has been a major probe, in recent years, to the studies on diffusion coefficient because of its several advantages over the conventional methods of analysis. In past, capillary¹⁻⁵, diaphragm⁶⁻¹⁰, optical¹¹⁻¹³ and conductivity^{14,15} methods were used for studying the diffusion of ions. These experimental techniques were not free from inherent problems of convection and streaming effects due to the flow of solvent. These methods require comparatively more time and rather a difficult experimental set-up. By using agar gel medium in place of diaphragm and capillary for such studies, the above shortcomings could be surmounted to a considerable extent. In 1930, Friedmann¹⁶ studied diffusion of non-electrolytes in agar gels and established a linear dependence of the diffusion coefficients on the gel concentration. Earlier work on the diffusion of electrolytes has been improved by the use of radiotracers. Thus Salvinien *et al.*¹⁷ have studied the diffusion of phosphate using ^{32}P , in gelatin gels. Their results do not follow the limiting law of Onsager and Fuoss¹⁸. Ionic diffusion in agar gel undoubtedly is influenced to some extent by the existence in the structure of fixed negative groups. In fact, agar gel has the remarkable property of immobilizing the solvent in a semi-rigid form and provides an ideal stationary medium. Here, the tracer-diffusion of $^{131}\text{I}^-$ in 0.01 M KNO_3 at 25° for 24, 48 and 72 h was studied by zone and front diffusion methods.

'Zone' diffusion :

A 1 mm zone of 2.5% bacto-agar containing 0.01 M KNO_3 labelled with $^{131}\text{I}^-$ was allowed to set in the centre of two columns of identical gel but containing the unlabelled electrolyte at the same concentration, in a 30 cm long pyrex tube of 1 cm diameter. The system was closed at both the ends and maintained at a constant temperature of 25° in

an automatically regulated thermostat for 24 h. After removal of the tube from thermostat, the gel column was withdrawn from the tube and sliced into series of 0.5 cm long samples. These samples were transferred to aluminium planchettes and carefully dehydrated in a hot air oven. The radioactivity of each sample was then counted under the conditions of constant geometry with the help of shielded G.M. counter of end-window type. A plot of activity vs the distance from the zone gives a symmetric Gaussian distribution satisfying Fick's second law,

$$C_{(x,t)} = \frac{C_0}{\sqrt{4\pi Dt}} \exp. (-x^2/4Dt) \quad (1)$$

where $C_{(x,t)}$ is the radioactivity at a distance x from the origin at time t and C_0 is the total radioactivity in the initial zone at $t=0$. A typical curve is presented in Fig. 1. From the slope of the plot

Fig 1. Tracer-diffusion of $^{131}\text{I}^-$ in 10^{-3} M KNO_3 electrolyte solution immobilized in 2.5% agar-agar gel at 25° by 'zone' diffusion method

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TABLE 1—TRACER-DIFFUSION COEFFICIENT OF $^{131}\text{I}^-$ IN 0.01 M KNO_3 IMMOBILIZED IN 2.5% GEL BY 'FRONT' DIFFUSION AT 25° FOR A PERIOD OF 24, 48 AND 72 h

Distance from plane of contact	t=24 h			t=48 h			t=72 h		
	$\frac{C}{C_0} = P(u)$	u	$D_{\text{expt}} \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sec}^{-1}$	$\frac{C}{C_0} = P(u)$	u	$D_{\text{expt}} \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sec}^{-1}$	$\frac{C}{C_0} = P(u)$	u	$D_{\text{expt}} \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sec}^{-1}$
5.0	0.9968	2.730	1.941	0.9887	2.280	1.392	0.9562	1.710	1.649
4.5	0.9922	2.420	2.001	0.9780	2.015	1.443	0.9382	1.540	1.647
4.0	0.9854	2.180	1.948	0.9263	1.708	1.587	0.9084	1.330	1.745
3.5	0.9694	1.873	2.021	0.9044	1.310	2.065	0.8724	1.140	1.818
3.0	0.9442	1.590	2.061	0.8655	1.105	2.133	0.8187	0.910	2.096
2.5	0.9084	1.330	2.044	0.8178	0.908	2.193	0.7692	0.738	2.214
2.0	0.9498	1.085	2.161	0.7565	0.695	2.396	0.7257	0.600	2.143
1.5	0.7591	0.705	2.619	0.6936	0.520	2.408	0.6670	0.433	2.315
1.0	0.6642	0.435	3.058	0.6315	0.335	2.578	0.6121	0.285	2.375
0.5	0.5645	0.214	3.159	0.5606	0.152	3.131	0.5504	0.130	2.854
	$\frac{C}{C_0} = 1 - P(u)$	u	$D_{\text{expt}} \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sec}^{-1}$	$\frac{C}{C_0} = 1 - P(u)$	u	$D_{\text{expt}} \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sec}^{-1}$	$\frac{C}{C_0} = 1 - P(u)$	u	$D_{\text{expt}} \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sec}^{-1}$
0.5	0.4171	0.210	3.280	0.4404	0.150	3.215	0.4505	0.125	3.086
1.0	0.3375	0.420	3.281	0.3710	0.330	2.657	0.3937	0.270	2.646
1.5	0.2424	0.700	2.657	0.2932	0.545	2.192	0.3416	0.411	2.569
2.0	0.1495	1.040	2.140	0.2162	0.785	1.878	0.2786	0.585	2.255
2.5	0.0927	1.325	2.060	0.1805	0.915	2.160	0.2342	0.783	2.244
3.0	0.0550	1.698	2.040	0.1305	1.125	2.058	0.1785	0.920	2.051
3.5	0.0301	1.880	2.006	0.0885	1.350	1.945	0.1263	1.138	1.825
4.0	0.0148	2.175	1.958	0.0423	1.725	1.556	0.0900	1.340	1.718
4.5	0.0071	2.450	1.952	0.0231	1.990	1.479	0.0602	1.550	1.626
5.0	0.0031	2.738	1.930	0.0122	2.250	1.429	0.0425	1.725	1.620

$\log C$ vs x^2 , the tracer diffusion coefficient D is determined from the relation,

$$\text{Slope} = \frac{1}{2.303 \times 4Dt} \quad (2)$$

'Front' diffusion :

In the 'zone' diffusion, the labelled ionic species is concentrated theoretically in the middle of an agar gel column of infinite length while in 'front' diffusion, half of the column consists of 2.5% agar gel containing 0.01 M KNO_3 solution labelled with $^{131}\text{I}^-$ and the other half consists of unlabelled solution of KNO_3 of same concentration immobilized in 2.5% agar gel. The tracer-diffusion of $^{131}\text{I}^-$ in 0.01 M KNO_3 solution was studied by this technique. Precautions were taken to avoid air bubbles during the setting of gel. Then the tubes were thermostated at 25° but for different time periods (i.e. 24, 48 and 72 h). At the end of these periods, gel column was cut into 0.5 cm samples and transferred to aluminium planchettes. These samples were then dried and radioactivity was counted. A plot of C/C_0 vs x (i.e. distance from plane of contact) gives the Gaussian distribution (Fig. 2) fitting with the following integrals of Fick's second law.

$$\frac{C}{C_0} = 0.5 \pm \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_0^u e^{-u^2/2} du \quad (3)$$

where $u = x / \sqrt{2Dt}$, C = concentration or radioactivity at a distance x from the plane of contact, and C_0 = initial concentration or radioactivity in the same amount of gel. (4)

Fig. 2. Tracer-diffusion of $^{131}\text{I}^-$ in 10^{-3} M KNO_3 electrolyte solution immobilized in 2.5% agar-agar gel at 25° by 'front' diffusion method: (O) 24, (*) 48 and (Δ) 72 h.

The positive and negative sign in equation (3) are for initially labelled and unlabelled parts of the gel column, respectively. From the standard tables¹⁹, the u values for the corresponding C/C_0 at a distance x from the plane of contact is found out and tracer-diffusion coefficient is calculated for each C/C_0 by equation (4).

The tracer-diffusion coefficients of $^{131}\text{I}^-$ ions in 0.01 M KNO_3 solution determined for different periods by 'zone' diffusion technique are found to be constant (at 25°, $D_{I^-} = 2.051 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sec}^{-1}$) whereas the values of diffusion coefficient by 'Front' diffusion method under identical conditions show a dependence on the period of diffusion and the distance from the plane of contact of the labelled and unlabelled gel columns (Table 1). In 'Front' diffusion technique, the tracer-diffusion coefficient

of $^{131}\text{I}^-$ in 0.01 M KNO_3 solution show slight irregularities near the plane of contact and then decreases slowly with distance.

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